

Sanctuary at Tell Qasile

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Tell Qasile is a Philistine peripheral site and religious sanctuary dating to the Iron Age, consisting of three superimposed temples which demonstrate the growth and transformation of the religious centre. Tell Qasile provides unparalleled insight into the development of Philistine ritual architecture from Iron I-IIA and unlike the Philistine pentapolis (Ashdod, Ashkelon, Tel Miqne-Ekron, Tell es-Safi/Gath and Gaza), the site of Tell Qasile is not mentioned in the Hebrew Bible. The earliest Philistine sanctuary comes from 1150-1100 BCE (Stratum XII) which places it amongst some of the earliest examples of Philistine sacral architecture available. The temples of Tell Qasile were integrated into the town plan, structure and surrounding buildings and were not isolated or free standing temple buildings. The main temple phases of Tell Qasile are labelled as Temple 319, Temple 200 and Temple 131. The Philistines were a group of the Sea Peoples, arriving to the coast of Canaan in 1200 BCE following the Bronze Age Collapse. The Philistines brought with them foreign religious, ritual and dietary practices, most likely migrating from the wider Aegean, Cyprus, Anatolia and Italy. The archaeological site of Tell Qasile and its finds are located in the Eretz museum in Tel Aviv, Israel. Little is known about Philistine religion, religious practise and deities, with the vast majority of research and discussion historically originating from the Hebrew bible and discourse of biblical archaeology. The Philistine pantheon may have consisted of three important deities throughout their existence: an Aegean goddess (possibly Ptgyh), Ashera (a Canaanite goddess), Dagon, Baal (son of Dagon). These deities were most likely not worshipped at the same time or period, but rather underwent a cycle as the Philistine cities became entwined with their local surroundings. Archaeology indicates that Philistine ritual activities may have included communal and elite feasting, votive offerings, animal sacrifice and the burning of incense.

Date Range: 1150 BCE - 586 BCE

Region: Tell Qasile

Region tags: Levant, Mediterranean Coast, Israel, Palestine

The ancient site of Tell Qasile is located north of the Yarkon river and 2km east of the Mediterranean coast. The ancient site was approximately 4 acres. The top of the Tell is 26m above sea level.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Mazar, A. 1980a. Excavations at Tell Qasile, Part One: The Philistine Sanctuary — Architecture

and Cult Objects. Jerusalem: Hebrew University

– Source 2: Mazar, A. 1980b. Excavations at Tell Qasile, Part Two: The Philistine Sanctuary – Various Finds, the Pottery, Conclusions, Appendixes. Jerusalem: Hebrew University

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.erezmuseum.org.il/e/101/>

– Source 1 Description: Tell Qasile Excavations Official Museum Page

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1949-51, 56; 1971-1974.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Tell Qasile

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Water source

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Notes: Tell Qasile was a port city, located in close proximity to rivers and the coast.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure
– No

↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

Notes: Temple 200 was built on top of the remains of Temple 319. Temple 200 is a small one roomed building with an off-axis entrance in on the east wall. Narrow platforms lined the walls of the temple.

– No

Notes: Shrine 300 is an auxiliary/ subsidiary room abutting the west wall of Temple 200, measuring 3.50 x 5.60 m.

– No

Notes: Stratum X Temple 131 is an extension and rebuilding of the previous Temple 200 with distinct changes to the internal plan, using three of the walls of the previous structure and continuing extension to the east. The temple is made up of benches, raised platforms, column bases, pillars, a threshold, chamber or holy of holies and a two-step platform altar (bamah).

– No

Notes: Temple 319 of Stratum XII is the earliest phase of the Philistine sanctuary. It is situated approximately in the centre of Area C below the floors and walls of the two later temples (temple 200, temple 131, shrine 300). The temple is square in shape and measures 6.40 x 6.60 meters (exterior) and 4.75 x 5.06 m (interior) with walls built of brick and no stone foundations.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The Philistine occupation of Tell Qasile spans ca. 1150-586 BCE

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The temple/s and shrine/s are part of a larger structure, however they are the main religious centre/s.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Social

Notes: Ritual related food consumption

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both communal and individual

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Strata XII-X

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: The various stages o

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: The cause destruction of the the earliest sanctuary phase (Stratum XII). Possibilities include fire, violent conquest or earthquake.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: Unknown. Insufficient data.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Unknown. Insufficient data.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Philistine pantheon may have consisted of three important deities throughout their existence: an Aegean goddess (possibly Ptgyh), Ashera (a Canaanite goddess), Dagon, Baal (son of Dagon). These deities were most likely not worshipped at the same time or period, but rather underwent a cycle as the Philistine cities became entwined with their local

surroundings.

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The temples were most likely used in the worship of multiple deities

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient evidence.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The possibility of ancestral worship cannot be ruled out, however the archaeological record provides no evidence.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Philistine scripture and/or sacred texts cease to exist. Despite the lack of existence in the archaeological record, the Philistines may have have sacred texts that did not survive.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The three stages of the ritual structures are superimposed. Stratum X, XI and XII demonstrate this development. The architecture and placement of the temple indicates that it was a central structure within the Tell Qasile complex.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Notes: Mudbrick, brick, stones, plaster, pottery sherd surfaces.

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No wooden columns were found atop the column bases, however contemporaneous temples from the Eastern Med suggest that wooden roof supports would have been utilised.

↳ Grass

– Field doesn't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Site is located on a kurkar ridge.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Mudbrick and worked stone

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The temples were furnished (benches, altars, platforms), however, decoration other than furnishing / installations may have been present. Material finds indicate that the building(s) were furnished with pottery vessels as well as wooden columns atop worked stone bases.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The archaeological record does not point toward worship of the dead due to the lack of written Philistine sources. However, it is highly probable the temples throughout their various phases may have been used for the worship of the dead.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Philistine pantheon may have consisted of three important deities throughout their existence: an Aegean goddess (possibly Ptgyh), Ashera (a Canaanite goddess), Dagon, Baal (son of Dagon).

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Tell Qasile votive vessel and anthropomorphic masks may indicate some form of a deity.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is believed the altars of the temple may have been used for sacrificial offerings, such as animals, plants and votive vessels, however the lack of faunal remains surrounding the altar suggests animal sacrifice was not common. The material finds (such as votive figurines and vessels, libation vessels, cult bowls) point toward ritual use.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Cultic vessels were uncovered in the temple complex, however whether they were definitively offering is unknown.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Whilst it can be stated that ritual occurred due to the nature of the archaeological finds, the exact type of ritual(s) is unknown. These acts may have included elite and communal feasting, offerings, sacrifice (such as puppy sacrifice, known from the Philistine site of Ekron) and incense burning.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Unknown.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It has been suggested that incense which may have been present in Philistine kylikes may have contained hallucinogens. P. W. Stockhammer (2012), *Performing the Practice Turn in Archaeology*. *Transcultural Studies* 1, 7-42.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: David Ben-Shlomo. *Philistine Iconography: A Wealth of Style and Symbolism*. Germany: Vandenhoeck and Ruprecht. isbn: 9783525543603.

Reference: Amihai Mazar. *EXCAVATIONS AT TELL QASILE: PART TWO: THE PHILISTINE SANCTUARY: VARIOUS FINDS, THE POTTERY, CONCLUSIONS, APPRNDIXED*. Institute of Archaeology, Hebrew University of Jerusalem: Qedem.

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